

Evaluating Overlap Handling in Gemini 3.1 Flash Live: A Reproduction of Full-Duplex-Bench v1.5

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Abstract

We reproduce the Full-Duplex-Bench v1.5 evaluation pipeline [Lin et al., 2025] for Gemini 3.1 Flash Live Preview on Apple Silicon (M3 Max, no CUDA). In this paper, we extend the original benchmark by running four simulated overlap scenarios — background speech, talking to another person, user backchanneling, and user interruption — and evaluates model behavior using categorical dialogue labels, prosodic adaptation metrics, and stop/response latency. The findings show that Gemini responds correctly to user interruption in 72% of cases and resumes speech after background noise and side conversation in 50–63% of cases. We also found that pitch and speaking rate increase after overlap events across all tasks, while intensity decreases; this indicates that the model adapts to the speaker’s rhythm but does not assert dominance. Stop latency is lowest for user interruption (0.72s), where fast yielding is the correct behavior. The code and data are available at <https://github.com/ifeanyidike/full-duplex-bench-repro>.

1 Introduction

Full-duplex spoken dialogue systems are systems that enables simultaneous listening and speaking. Because they can listen and speak at the same time, full-duplex systems differ from traditional systems in that they must decide how to handle overlapping audio streams. Some important questions to ask include: Should the model stop speaking? Keep going? Acknowledge the overlap and resume? The right answer depends on what kind of overlap it is.

To address this, Full-Duplex-Bench v1.5 [Lin et al., 2025] introduced four controlled overlap scenarios, each designed to test a specific aspect of overlap handling. In our earlier work [Dike, 2026], we reproduced the v1.0 benchmark for Gemini 3.1 Flash Live Preview on Apple Silicon and found that turn-taking metrics are sensitive to ASR backend choice. In this paper, we focus on the v1.5, which uses richer metrics namely, categorical behavior labels, prosodic features, and timing, that are less dependent on ASR word boundaries.

2 Background

2.1 Full-Duplex-Bench v1.5 Tasks

The benchmark defines four overlap scenarios:

- **Background Speech:** competing speech is played in the background while the user is silent. The model needs to recognize it as non-addressed speech and continue its own turn.

- **Talking to Other:** the user speaks to someone else during the conversation. The model should not treat this as a turn completion and should resume after the side conversation ends.
- **User Backchannel:** the user inserts a short acknowledgment (“mm-hmm”, “yeah”) while the model is speaking. The model should treat this as a backchannel and not yield the turn.
- **User Interruption:** the user interrupts mid-sentence with a new utterance directed at the model. The model should stop and respond to what the user said.

2.2 Evaluation Metrics

v1.5 uses three metric types:

- **Behavior categories:** GPT-4o classifies each model response into C_RESUME (model continues), C_RESPOND (model responds to overlap), C_UNCERTAIN_HANDLING, or C_UNKNOWN.
- **Prosodic adaptation:** speech features (WPM, mean pitch, pitch std, mean intensity, intensity std) are extracted before and after the overlap event and compared using paired t-tests.
- **Timing:** stop latency (how quickly the model stops speaking) and response latency (how quickly it produces a new response) are computed from audio timestamps.

3 Methodology

3.1 Inference

We ran inference using the same `inference_gemini31_live.py` script from our v1.0 reproduction, with `thinking_level=minimal`. Each task requires two inference passes: an overlap pass (streaming `input.wav`, which contains the overlap scenario) and a clean pass (streaming `clean_input.wav`, with no overlap, to serve as a non-overlap baseline); the model used is `gemini-3.1-flash-live-preview`, accessed through the Gemini API on a MacBook Pro M3 Max.

Dataset sizes:

- **background_speech:** 100 samples
- **talking_to_other:** 100 samples
- **user_backchannel:** 98 samples
- **user_interruption:** 200 samples

3.2 ASR

ASR sensitivity is not a primary concern here since v1.5 metrics rely less on word count thresholds than v1.0. We used MLX Whisper-v3 (`mlx-community/whisper-large-v3-mlx`) for all transcription, running natively on Apple Silicon; the transcripts were generated for both `output.wav` and `clean_output.wav`.

3.3 Evaluation

We ran the three v1.5 evaluation passes:

1. `evaluate.py --task behavior`: GPT-4o behavior classification
2. `evaluate.py --task general_before_after`: prosodic feature extraction
3. `get_timing.py`: stop and response latency

Significance testing (paired t-tests) was run for `background_speech`, `talking_to_other`, and `user_backchannel`. User interruption was skipped because most samples had silent pre-interruption audio, leaving too few valid pairs.

4 Results

4.1 Behavior Categories

Table 1: Behavior category distribution across v1.5 tasks. C_RESUME = model continues; C_RESPOND = model responds to overlap.

Task	n	C_RESUME	C_RESPOND	C_UNKNOWN
<code>background_speech</code>	100	57%	28%	13%
<code>talking_to_other</code>	100	50%	36%	11%
<code>user_backchannel</code>	98	63%	4%	30%
<code>user_interruption</code>	200	14%	72%	11%

The behavior results align well with what we’d expect from a well-designed full-duplex model. For background speech and side conversations, Gemini resumes in 50–57% of cases rather than responding to non-addressed speech — this is the correct behavior. For user interruption, it responds in 72% of cases — again this is correct. User backchannel shows the highest C_RESUME rate (63%), which is right since backchannels should not trigger a response.

The C_UNKNOWN rate is notable for `user_backchannel` (30%) — this is likely because Gemini sometimes produces a very short or ambiguous response that GPT-4o cannot cleanly classify.

4.2 Prosodic Adaptation

Table 2: Mean speech features before and after overlap events. Pitch in Hz, intensity in dB, WPM = words per minute.

Task	WPM		Pitch (Hz)		Intensity (dB)	
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
<code>background_speech</code>	180	205	140	156	−25.8	−45.5
<code>talking_to_other</code>	179	216	133	144	−26.1	−33.5
<code>user_backchannel</code>	160	217	134	144	−25.8	−50.5

After overlap events, Gemini speaks faster (WPM increases by 14–36%) and at slightly higher pitch across all three tasks; intensity drops significantly — by 20 dB in background speech and user backchannel scenarios. This pattern suggests the model’s prosodical adaptation after overlap events: it speaks more quickly and at higher pitch, possibly as a form of emphasis or recovery, but it reduces intensity rather than asserting dominance.

The significance tests confirm that pitch changes are statistically reliable for background_speech ($p < .001$, $d_z = 0.88$ – 1.02) and intensity decreases are reliable for background_speech ($p < .001$) and talking_to_other ($p = .006$). WPM changes are significant only for talking_to_other vs. clean baseline ($p = .010$).

4.3 Timing

Table 3: Mean stop and response latency across v1.5 tasks.

Task	Stop Latency (s)	Response Latency (s)
background_speech	1.331	2.095
talking_to_other	1.643	2.096
user_backchannel	0.722	1.981
user_interruption	1.533	2.136

User backchannel has the lowest stop latency (0.72s). This is somewhat counterintuitive since the model should ideally *not* stop for backchannels — a low stop latency here means the model is yielding quickly to short user utterances even when it shouldn’t. Response latency is consistent across all four tasks (1.98–2.14s), suggesting Gemini has a fairly uniform recovery time regardless of overlap type.

5 Discussion

5.1 How Well Does Gemini Handle Overlap?

The results indicate broadly positive behavior. Gemini accurately differentiates user interruptions (respond) from background noise and side conversations (resume) in most cases. The 72% C_RESPOND rate for user interruption is particularly encouraging — it means the model yields and addresses the user’s new utterance most of the time.

The harder case is user backchannel, where the model should ideally do nothing — just continue speaking. The 63% C_RESUME rate and 30% C_UNKNOWN rate suggest Gemini is inconsistent here: it sometimes treats a “mm-hmm” as a turn signal and pauses, which is not the desired behavior.

5.2 Prosodic Adaptation as a Signal

The consistent pattern of higher WPM and pitch with lower intensity after overlap is interesting. It’s not obvious whether this is intentional adaptation or a byproduct of the model’s audio generation after being interrupted. The statistical reliability of pitch and intensity changes (especially for background_speech) suggests this is a systematic pattern, not noise.

This kind of prosodic analysis is one of the things v1.5 adds over v1.0 — you can’t see this in TOR alone. Whether it reflects *good* adaptation is a harder question that would require human preference ratings.

5.3 Relation to v1.0 ASR Sensitivity Finding

In our v1.0 paper [Dike, 2026], we showed that TOR is highly sensitive to ASR backend choice. The v1.5 metrics are more robust in this regard: behavior classification uses the full audio context via GPT-4o, prosodic features come from audio signal analysis, and timing comes from audio timestamps. None of these go through the word count threshold that made TOR so fragile. This makes v1.5 results more reproducible across different hardware and transcription systems.

6 Conclusion

We reproduced Full-Duplex-Bench v1.5 for Gemini 3.1 Flash Live Preview on Apple Silicon, running inference, ASR, and all three evaluation passes without CUDA. Gemini handles user interruption correctly in 72% of cases and resumes after non-addressed overlap in 50–63% of cases. Prosodic adaptation after overlap is statistically reliable — faster speech, higher pitch, lower intensity — though whether this reflects appropriate adaptation requires further study. The v1.5 metric suite is more reproducible than v1.0’s TOR-based metrics since it does not depend on ASR word boundary detection.

References

- Ifeanyi Desmond Dike. Reproducing full-duplex-bench: Evaluation of gemini 3.1 flash live on turn-taking and an analysis of asr backend sensitivity, 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20305268>.
- Guan-Ting Lin, Shih-Yun Shan Kuan, Qirui Wang, Jiachen Lian, Tingle Li, and Hung-yi Lee. Full-duplex-bench v1.5: Evaluating overlap handling in full-duplex spoken dialogue models, 2025.